
The Main Aspects of Social Protection of Children in Uzbekistan

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Abstract: The article discusses the ways to improve the social protection of families and children in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Based on data analysis, it was obtained various options to improve the child protection system in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Key words: social policy, system, social protection, children, social work, vulnerable groups of the population, social support.

INTRODUCTION

The system of social protection of children and family in the modern world is one of the important institutions for the implementation of socio - economic policy of the state. The effectiveness of this system largely forms the basis for the economic, social, cultural development of the country and society and ensures the active resolution of childhood problems.

In the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022 – 2026 President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Mr. Shavkat Mirziyoyev indicates the further implementation of comprehensive measures to strengthen family health, protect motherhood and childhood, expand access of mothers and children to qualified medical services, provide them with specialized and high - tech medical care, reduce infant and child mortality [1].

LITERATURE REVIEW

In the literature, when discussing the social aspects of the process of social assistance to children, various terms are found: “legal protection of childhood”, “protection of the rights of child”, “protection of children’s rights”, “social protection of childhood”. In the last phrase, it is necessary to add one more important concept - “family”, so as an effective solution to childhood problems is impossible without considering issues related to the functioning of the family as a social institution that ensures the reproduction and sustainable development of society [2].

The category “social protection system for children and families” seems to be the most optimal, since it includes not only several key concepts - “social”, “system”, “protection”, “childhood”, “family”, but also implies a holistic, comprehensive, humanistic – based concept of ensuring the social, economic, psychological well-being of the child.

The use of the word “social” in the context of discussing problems of a social nature that people in difficult life situations may experience means that the state understands their objectively subjective nature. In other words, “social” implies the involvement in the problem – solving process not only of an individual, group or family, but also social, economic, and legal resources.

The commonly used meaning of the word “protection” in Uzbek languages is associated with protection, protection from encroachments, from danger, from hostile actions [3], while its special meaning is with the legal status of an individual, its rights and freedoms, and the constitutional powers of citizens [4].

Any social protection system presupposes those for whom it is oriented and directed, for whom it functions - in this case, for children and family. Foreign literature on social work, sociology and psychology has long emphasized the social nature of these social phenomena. Mr. Kohn I. S. draws attention to the consideration of children as a socio - demographic group that reflects a certain autonomous socio - cultural reality. The vision of the child (and childhood) as a social subject presupposes its autonomy, a value - based attitude towards it and, consequently, consistent protection of its rights [5].

As for the concept of “family”, then, as a rule, the expressions “social institution” or “primary unit of society” are used in any of its definitions [6].

It is difficult to find a single definition of the concept “social protection system” in the specialized literature. However, an analysis of various literary sources devoted to this category allows us to talk about the identification of several main features - integrity, unity, interaction, functionality [7].

The most general and comprehensive definition of social protection is presented in the course of lectures by Pavlenyuk P. D. dealing with problems of social work. Social protection is “a system of priorities and mechanisms for implementation of legislatively fixed social, legal and economic guarantees for citizens, government bodies at all levels, other institutions, as well as a system of social services designed to provide a certain level of social protection, helping to achieve a socially acceptable standard of living of the population in accordance with the specific conditions of social development” [8]. It follows from this definition that social protection is always a system of optimally functioning and interacting components aimed at the observance and realization of human rights and freedoms, which must be guaranteed by the state [9].

According to Yakushev L., the social protection system of each country is based on three criteria, which are summarized in the form of principles “what do you have”, “what have you done”, “who are you”. These criteria represent the main criteria for the provision of benefits: need, fulfillment of established duties or belonging to a certain group or category of the population. We can say that the well-known classification of social states by Swedish scientist Esping - Andersen is based on these criteria, based on which the social protection system of most countries is built [10].

The main features of a “social state” include ensuring a decent human life and creating conditions for its free development in strong legal field. In other words, a social state is possible only in a state governed by the rule of law, in which the main component of the social protection system, focused on supporting the socially vulnerable, is legislative framework [11]. Uzbekistan sets itself the task of creating a humanitarian democratic legal state [12].

Esping – Andersen identified three main models of social states: the liberal regime (liberal), the conservative - corporatist regime (conservative - corporate) and the liberal - socialist or social - democratic regime (social - democratic) [13].

The liberal model of social protection (based on the principle of “what you have”) is limited to targeted assistance only to those who have no other income. This type includes all English - speaking countries, including the United Kingdom, and Japan. The conservative-corporate model of social protection operates on the principle of “what have you done” and is focused on preserving the quality of life that was achieved by a person during his working life, and not on income redistribution or poverty eradication. This model is typical for most Western European countries. In the social - democratic system of social protection (the principle of “who you are”) used in the Scandinavian countries, income equalization, universal employment and regulation of labor relations dominate [14].

From all of the above, we can conclude that there are two main components in the social protection system - strong legislation and criteria for the provision of social assistance [15].

Returning to the discussion of the concept of “the system of social protection of childhood and family”, it is necessary to consider the views of specialists on the features of its development. So,

according to the Russian author Stepanov O.V., the development of the system of social protection of children depends on the peculiarities of the development of all social institutions of society; is determined by the needs of society in ensuring the reproduction of the population; is determined by the level of socio - economic status of the country and its sociocultural characteristics [16].

METHODOLOGY

The content of the article is based on various research methods, primarily on assessing the social protection system through interviews with stakeholders. The assessment critically assessed the strategies used, identified lessons learned and best practices, measures that accelerate the achievement of sustainable results in working with children in Uzbekistan, especially from the most vulnerable categories.

The assessment was aimed at analyzing the relevance, efficiency, effectiveness, sustainability, coherence and, where possible, impact of the strategies adopted to achieve results of country – specific programs. It is concluded that the effectiveness of the system of social protection of children and family is based on the presence of the listed structural components in it, and in subsequent parts of this article we will try to analyze the main of these components in relation to the system of social protection of children in Uzbekistan.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Uzbekistan is one of the largest investors in social protection across middle-income countries, with investment on a par with a number of high-income countries. However, the national social protection system is in need of reform to maximize value for money and ensure that many of those in need – who are currently excluded - can access it. This includes millions of the most vulnerable children in Uzbekistan.

Uzbekistan has a youthful population. Around 33 per cent of the population are children aged 0-17 years while 57 per cent of the population are 30 years of age or younger. Only 8 per cent of the population is 60 years of age or above. Most children live on low incomes and poverty is highest among children, adults who are likely to be raising children and those of age 80 years and above. Families tend to be relatively large in Uzbekistan and often contain multiple generations: nearly one third of children live in a household with seven or more members.

Tab 1. Distribution of households according to number of family generations, by place of residence, in percentages [17]

#	Households	Total	Urban	Rural
1.	One – generation household	6	12	4
2.	Parents and adult children	5	8	4
3.	Parents and children under 25	51	49	52
4.	Three or four generations	38	30	40
5.	Skipped generation household	0	1	0
	Total	100	100	100

Uzbekistan is currently in a position to take advantage of a demographic dividend but, for this is to happen, it will be crucial to invest in children to ensure a skilled future labor force while also creating sufficient good quality jobs. Overall dependency ratios will not rise significantly until 2040 and, indeed, will fall in the 2030s. However, once dependency ratios increase, the importance of a skilled workforce will grow even more since, to compensate for the lower proportion of people in the labor force, the productivity of those in employment will need to increase.

Probably as a result of low incomes, some young children are experiencing undernutrition. Almost 9 per cent of children are stunted and stunting has an irreversible impact on a child’s cognitive development, which can affect their future productivity. For example, children who are stunted are likely to earn 26 per cent less as adults than their non-stunted peers.

Uzbekistan has made great strides towards ensuring high levels of access to basic education, although the quality of the schooling received may be lower than desired. Eleven years of primary and secondary schooling are compulsory, starting at age 7. Overall, 99 per cent of children aged 7 to 15 years were enrolled in an educational institution during the 2022/23 academic school year, and boys and girls were equally likely to be enrolled. However, there is relatively low access to pre-school education with significant regional disparities. Furthermore, young children from the poorest households are 1.4 times less likely to benefit from pre-school education than those from more affluent households.

Children with disabilities have even fewer opportunities than their non - disabled peers. While access to general education is nearly universal, around 13 per cent of disabled children aged 7-15 years are not enrolled while nearly a third of young people with disabilities fail to complete any diploma.

Limited access to education poses further challenges for young people. Nationwide, only 12 per cent of young people aged 25 - 30 years have completed a university education. Those in urban areas are twice as likely to achieve a tertiary degree compared to those in rural areas (22 per cent versus 9 per cent). Income disparities in access to higher education are even more pronounced. Only 3 per cent of young people aged 25 - 30 years in the bottom quintile have completed higher education compared to 23 per cent among those in the most affluent quintile. There is also a gender disparity with a four-percentage point difference in favor of males (10 per cent for women and 14 per cent for men). Young people with disabilities experience significantly lower levels of educational attainment, with nearly a third not having completed any diploma.

After schooling, the transition from the education system to the labor market is challenging for most young people. This is illustrated by the high levels of 'NEETs,' a term used to describe young people who are not in employment, nor in education or training. Out of the country's 8.5 million young people aged 15 - 29 years, an estimated 42 per cent (3.6 million) are not in employment, education or training. Nationwide, the female NEET rate is 66 per cent, compared to 34 per cent for young males. Among young people with severe disabilities, the NEET rate is 77 per cent, rising to 91 per cent of those with profound disabilities.

Uzbekistan currently invests 9.7 per cent of GDP in its national social protection system. The system is financed by a combination of social insurance contributions and general tax revenues. As in high-income countries, Uzbekistan has built a national lifecycle social protection system, with schemes addressing the challenges faced by people across the lifecycle, from childhood to old age. There are, however, significant imbalances in levels of investment across the lifecycle. 72 per cent of all investment – or 6.95 per cent of GDP – is in old age pension schemes, despite a relatively young population. This is higher than the level of investment in some high-income countries with much larger populations of older persons.

Overall, 23 per cent of the population is a direct recipient of some type of social protection benefit, while 54 per cent of the population lives in a household accessing a social protection benefit. Among children aged 0-17 years, 54 per cent live in a household receiving a social protection benefit while, among young people aged 18-30 years, the proportion is 44 per cent.

Tab 2. Proportion of households including at least one person of specific age groups, in percentages [18]

#	Households	Proportion
1.	With children under 18	78
2.	With youth 18 - 29	60
3.	With working age adults 30+	89
4.	With people of retirement age	39

In fact, as Tab 2 shows, 78 per cent of households in Uzbekistan include at least one child of 0 - 17 years while 60 per cent include a young person of 18 - 29 years. Around 39 per cent of household include a member of pensionable age.

Despite the fact that some social protection schemes are targeted at the poorest families, among households living below a poverty line set at 50 per cent of median income, coverage is only 48 per cent, meaning that 52 per cent of the poorest households are excluded from any support by the national social protection system. Given that a range of programs are financed by social insurance contributions, it is unsurprising that many people with higher incomes – in particular older people – are able to access support.

Uzbekistan's child benefit system comprises three main schemes: the Childcare Allowance for families with a child under the age of 2 years; the Family Allowance for families with children aged 2-14 years; and, a Child Disability Benefit. Coverage is low for the first two schemes, which are targeted at the poorest families. The system of child benefits used to be universal when the Soviet Union fell but coverage has fallen significantly as poverty-targeting has been increasingly introduced. Currently, only 17 per cent of children are able to access a child benefit. The Child Disability Benefit is a key program for many of Uzbekistan's most vulnerable children. However, the scheme only reaches 52 per cent of children with severe disabilities despite it being offered on a universal basis to children with disabilities. Clearly, many families are struggling to overcome barriers to access.

Young people can also access public works programs and unemployment benefits although they reach only a very small number. While young families living in poverty can, in theory, access the Low-Income Allowance, in reality, due to the limited size of the program, very few do. The Low-Income Allowance is a very small program, reaching only 61,500 families. In its current state, there appears to be little value offered by the Low-Income Allowance and it may be preferable to transfer its funding to the child benefit system.

Uzbekistan's lifecycle social protection system has had a significant impact on poverty and inequality. In the absence of a social protection system, Uzbekistan would have a significantly higher poverty rate and higher level of inequality. In fact, as a result of social protection the poverty rate falls by 39 per cent, the poverty gap is halved and the Gini - coefficient decreases from 0.524 to 0.445.

Overall, the child poverty rate has reduced by over a third and the poverty gap by nearly half as a result of the entire social protection system. However, these reductions are largely due to the old age pension. In fact, the child benefits themselves are responsible for only 12 per cent of the overall reduction in the child poverty rate and 17 per cent of the reduction in the poverty gap. Indeed, it is the old age pension that is being relied upon to support children although this is not its purpose. Rather, the child benefit system should be playing a much bigger role in improving child wellbeing.

The limited contribution of the child benefits is mainly due to low investment and low coverage. Many recipients of the Childcare and Family Allowances only receive the benefits for short periods of time. This suggests that the Mahallas – which are responsible for selecting recipients – are rationing an inadequate number of benefits by sharing them across the high number of families who are eligible but unable to access the scheme at any particular time. The downside of this rationing is that it significantly reduces the effectiveness of the child benefits, since families are unable to access regular and predictable transfers for enough time for them to have a significant impact.

Another challenge is the poor performance of poverty-targeting. Both the Childcare and Family Allowance are targeted at families living in poverty: the eligibility criteria for the schemes are that recipients should live on less than the equivalent of 1.5 times the value of the minimum wage across each person in the family. Around half of households with children nationally are eligible for the schemes, yet only a small proportion are selected (63 per cent of households with eligible

children are excluded from the Childcare Allowance and 88 per cent from the Family Allowance). In a context of high levels of informal employment, it is very challenging to identify incomes accurately. Indeed, most eligible families have similar levels of income, which makes it difficult to differentiate between them. And, of course, family incomes can vary significantly over short periods of time, making targeting even more challenging.

A potential negative impact of poverty-targeting – as used in the Childcare and Family Allowances – is that it can disincentivize recipient families from seeking work. Since only poor families can receive the benefits, if recipients enter the labour market, they are likely to have their benefits removed. As a result, poverty traps are often created by poverty targeting, with families unintentionally encouraged by the state not to work and to remain poor. Further, recipients of the Childcare Allowance risk losing the benefit when a family member enters the workforce. The amount of the Childcare Allowance – at 50 per cent of GDP per capita – may be larger than the income to be earned from employment.

RECOMMENDATIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

It is possible for Uzbekistan to build a comprehensive child benefit system in 2020 with only a slight initial increase in investment over the current level of spending in the Childcare and Family Allowances, with further small annual increases as the age of eligibility for the child benefits increases each year, by one year each time. Three options are proposed in this article:

Option 1 begins with children aged 0 - 3 years and would reach children aged 0 - 13 years by 2030 and 0 - 17 years by 2034. In line with the current child benefit system, it would offer a higher transfer value for children aged up to 2 years: so, children aged 0 - 1 years would receive UZS150,000 per month while older children would receive UZS100,000 per month.

Option 2 begins with a higher age group of 0 - 7 years so that children aged 0 - 17 years can be reached by 2030. All children would, however, receive a constant transfer value of UZS100,000 per month.

Option 3 is similar to Option 1 in that it begins with children aged 0 - 3 years and would reach children aged 0 - 13 years by 2030 and 0 - 17 years by 2034. The difference with Option 1 is that it would pay a higher transfer value of UZS150,000 per month.

While the options are not universal, they would aim to reach 75 per cent of children in their age category. Rather than targeting the poorest children – which is impossible to do accurately – the schemes would aim to exclude better-off families, which should be easier to undertake. This is a form of means-testing called an affluence test and it has been used successfully in South Africa and the United Kingdom. Most families in Uzbekistan have relatively similar incomes and it is only among the richest quintile that there is greater differentiation. Therefore, selecting recipients on this basis should be easier than targeting the poorest children.

The three options would have much larger impacts on child wellbeing than the current system of Childcare and Family Allowances. For example, by 2030, compared to a situation of no child benefits, the national poverty rate would fall by between 21.3 and 28.2 per cent, a very significant improvement on 7.2 per cent reduction resulting from the current poverty - targeted Childcare and Family Allowances. Furthermore, the child poverty rate would fall by between 26 and 35 per cent, compared to the 8.9 per cent reduction that is generated by the current system.

The cost of the three options is relatively modest. Option 1 requires the lowest level of investment, at 0.8 per cent of GDP in 2020, similar to the likely spending on benefits for children in 2020 by the current national social protection system, if it were consolidated. The further expansion of the child benefit system would take place gradually, as the age of eligibility increases by one year, each year. The cost of this expansion could be easily covered by the additional taxation that would be generated by economic growth, without any need to increase the tax base or introduce new taxes. By 2030, the level of investment required for Option 1 would be 1.29 per cent of GDP, similar to what Uzbekistan was spending on the Childcare and Family Allowances as recently as

2011. Options 2 and 3 would cost a little more, at 1.6 and 1.82 per cent of GDP respectively. Once all children aged 0 - 17 years are incorporated in the schemes, the cost of each option as a percentage of GDP would begin to fall, due to future demographic change and reductions in fertility.

While young people who are parents of children will benefit significantly from reforms to the child benefit system, social protection for young people requires a different approach to social protection for children since there needs to be a clear focus on facilitating the access of young people to work.

Options to improve social protection for young people include: ensuring that access to disability benefits is not limited to those who are assessed as unable to work so that disabled young people who want to work are able to receive financial support; introducing new social insurance products into the Pension Fund, including employment, maternity, paternity and sickness insurance; offering more jobs financed by Government, potentially using savings from reforms to the pension system; and, providing free childcare to support mothers of young children to return to work after childbirth.

Although Uzbekistan is one of the largest investors in social protection across middle - income countries, the design of its system is not aligned to the challenges faced by the country. While Uzbekistan is also a high investor in disability benefits, a high proportion of people with disabilities, including children with disabilities, are not receiving them. And, importantly, following budget cuts over the past twenty years, the vast majority of children are unable to access the child benefit system.

It is essential that much more is done to support young children and reverse the cuts in financing of the child benefits that have happened over the past 20 years. The suggested reforms to the child benefit system would bring Uzbekistan in line with a middle-income country such as Mongolia and, more importantly, help establish the type of child benefit system that has been successful in high-income countries. Combined with reforms to the old age pension and disability benefit systems to ensure universal coverage, improvements to other schemes addressing additional lifecycle risks such as maternity, unemployment and sickness, and investments in active labour market programs – including the provision of free childcare – the effectiveness of the national social protection system could be significantly enhanced. A minimum level of income security could be provided to the majority of the population while also generating greater economic growth and enhancing social cohesion. And, Uzbekistan would be much better placed to take advantage of the demographic dividend and avoid it turning into a curse.

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